

BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY AND MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR A NEW MANAGEMENT APPROACH IN THE CONTEXT OF BIG DATA FOR AVIATION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Purpose – *The purpose of this article is to define the current context of the fourth industrial revolution and to highlight the importance of making sense of the huge amount of available data for data-driven business decisions.*

Methodology/approach - *In this paper, we analyzed the general impact of the cutting-edge technologies from the sphere of AI, like Blockchain and machine learning, especially in the aviation industry.*

Findings – *Now, more than ever, emerging technologies will take the phenomenon of globalization to a whole new level. In a data-driven business ecosystem, traditional management it is no longer an option.*

Research limitations/implications – *Not every company is ready to implement the proposed technologies. The right path is changing the culture towards digitalization and step by step adding new technological tools.*

Practical implications – *Organizations that will understand the benefits of the Blockchain technology and data analytics tools will have an exponential business growth.*

Originality/value – *The concept of the Blockchain technology was emphasized in a small application developed in the Python programming language. This program presents an innovative approach for the supply chain management of an aircraft's components.*

Key words: *Big Data, The fourth revolution, Aviation Industry.*

Introduction

Our modern society will never be the same. In every phase of globalization, technology has played an important role in the world's economy, being a catalyst for this process of transforming the world into a single unit, with a common policy and economy.

We are certainly living in a world ruled by technology, which is indispensable for both industry and common user. The term "technology" refers to a very wide area of innovations which are not all applicable in our current society. Choosing the right technology for the right industry can be challenging. Often, managers are either too confident in the benefits of a technology and make things complicated in their organizations or are either too scared or skeptical to realize the advantages of embracing the new technologies. Thanks to a cheaper storage media, faster processing methods, faster communication channels and better algorithms, data can be stored and processed in huge quantities, giving organizations the opportunity to achieve new performances. However, the process of digitalization and technologicalization implies downsides if they are not properly understood and implemented in the context of each industry.

The current context of the third millennium is the digital reality generated by the expansion of data. A situation that needs new business approaches, new marketing campaigns and new tools for interpreting and analyzing data.

Big data, or in other words, information of extreme, diverse and complex dimensions governs around any modern organization today.(Youssra Riahi & Sara Riahi, 2018) Whether we are talking about employees who produce a multitude of data (emails, reports, recordings, social media, etc.) or suppliers and customers who generate various data by the nature of their actions, the data is produced throughout the entire chain of a company. The challenge is to have quick access to data and transform it in structured information. The ability of storing all this information is worthless if there is no capacity to analyze and interpret this data.

According to a study on the evolution of data globally so far and estimated until 2025, there is an exponential increase over the years (Statista, 2020).

Figure 1. The evolution of data globally so far and estimated until 2025(Statista, 2020)

Research problem

The strategy based on the idea of continuous improvement and meeting customer requirements is alive and well rooted in the strategy of any successful organization in the world. Achieving these objectives is due to the implementation of quality improvement concepts. The positive results of a company are never accidental, on the contrary, they appear due to the implementation of well-established methods of quality improvement. However, traditional approach of quality improvements is no longer a viable solution in a system governed by data.

For instance, “Lean” thinking refers to the fluency of a process and consists in eliminating all unnecessary elements and simplifying the whole process to make it faster and easier to follow. (Yagulawathi Thangarajoo, 2015). The ideal result of applying the “Lean” philosophy is a shorter, faster and a more productive process, which will satisfy both the customer and the employees.

“Lean” management is about speed and simplification, about delivering an order in the shortest possible time without compromising quality and by eliminating unnecessary elements that do not add value. This method of streamlining a process involves using only the resources strictly necessary. Thus, the goal is to do more with less. Basically, a “Lean” process is “smooth” because it aims to achieve a maximum yield for each available resource.

Therefore, the “Lean” approach is a well-known fundamental concept of optimizing a process which is still valid nowadays. Now, more than ever, these principles can be applied in the current industry, with the help of technology. Starting from the root quality principles, discovered in the past, mixing them with the latest tools of automatization and data analytics, improvements can be amplified in an unprecedented way.

Research Methodology

The emergence of a new industrial revolution is a natural evolution of the society in which we live, given the expansion of technology in the recent years. The fourth industrial revolution completes the previous revolutions generated by the discovery of the steam engine, electricity and innovations in the field of information and communication technology (Mustafa Ertunc Tat & Melih Cemal Kushan, 2017). The main features of this new industrial revolution are connectivity and digitization with obvious benefits both in terms of process efficiency and in terms of economics.

These technological developments are also applicable in the air transportation, where the safety and quality of the technical interventions should be always at the highest standards. All these technologies that are based on automation, IoT, artificial intelligence, digitization, data analysis, 3D printing and augmented reality have the potential to change the aviation industry by generating new mechanisms to make it not only more efficient but even safer.

The aviation industry realized that a predictive maintenance activity could be prepared in advance, based on real-time information obtained directly during flight. At the time of landing of an aircraft, the technical staff would be able to already know what is wrong with the aircraft and act accordingly. It is indeed a challenge, but it can be achieved in the current technological context. Theoretically, this situation could be possible due to the connectivity between the aircraft sensors and the ground receptors or through a satellite. Identifying the cause of a defect even during the flight could automate the maintenance activity, by notifying the maintenance staff and ordering the parts needed for the repair process.

An aircraft is equipped with many sensors capable of recording data related to the evolution of the flight parameters (Victor Emmanuell BADEA & Alin ZAMFIROIU & Radu BONCEA, 2018). The cumulative analysis of these parameters using specific technologies of the fourth industrial revolution would help specialists to understand on time the behavior of an aircraft, so maintenance intervention can be performed before faults occur. Identifying a pattern in the way a technical system will fail is now possible with the help of artificial intelligent. Predictive maintenance translates into aviation safety because it has the potential to avoid certain accidents and extend the life of an aircraft. Anticipating technical problems before they strike and spread in the system has always been a concern for specialists in this field. Synchronizing predictive maintenance with logistics activities will lead to a much higher aircraft availability, time and financial resources saved.

Moreover, the fourth industrial revolution bring to light the benefits of using augmented reality. The lack of expertise or experience can be compensated with the help of augmented reality, directly from the user's tablet. This type of technology that combines actual reality with virtual reality develops an augmented reality which provides more suggestive instructions for technicians. The technician's activity is monitored and verified in real time. Difficult situations can be resolved through a video conference, where a more experienced specialist, located anywhere in the world, can provide real-time assistance. At the same time, artificial intelligence algorithms process the data collected through the system, identifying new risks and activities that can be improved or optimized.

An aircraft technical logbook is a specific document which provides information about the maintenance status and operational data of an aircraft. It is the main communication tool between pilots and a maintenance organization. Pilots see the condition of the aircraft and report any malfunctions after the flight. Its digitalization will ensure top management that all tasks are consulted, understood, and executed in full volume (Abd Hakim Haruzly & Ghadzali I.F.S & Fadzil Adly Ishak, 2019). This way of working involves the implementation of an information system at every level of the organization powered by intelligence algorithms for data analytics. All the necessary information for the technicians is managed in electronic format and accessed through individual tablets.

The implementation of an electronic logbook would allow a real-time data interpretation and a fast identification of optimal solutions to fix a malfunction in a much shorter period. A digitized technical logbook synchronized with an integrated maintenance system and combined with a friendly interface would allow an efficient and a fast communication with all the personnel involved in the flight preparation activity of an aircraft.

Digitalization is the first step in the attempt to improve management activities in an organization. Further, after the first step is completed, as a result, more data will be generated. Therefore, the second step is to find an innovative method of storing data – Blockchain solution.

The Blockchain platform in the supply chain management of an aircraft's components

Airlines, aircraft production companies and maintenance organizations focus on creating a digitalized environment by implementing emerging technologies such as cloud computing, IoT and blockchain.

Implementing a Blockchain platform defines a new paradigm where the Internet of Things (IoT) play an important role to ensure an interconnected ecosystem. "Internet of Things" is the promoter of the fourth industrial revolution due to the development opportunities that this concept brings to the industry. The principle of connecting household devices to the Internet also applies to industrial processes.

The Internet of Things, or IoT, refers to the billions of devices around the world that are now connected to the internet, all collecting and sharing data. Due to the recent improvement in the computing power system and wireless network infrastructure it is possible to transfer almost anything at impressive speeds.

However, once the transfer is realized, sensitive data is not safely stored. This is why Blockchain technology defines a new standard in data storage.

Blockchain is an immutable and distributed digital database which uses cryptography to secure the trade data (Ahrash Aleshi, Remzi Seker, Radu F. Babiceanu 2019). The resulted digital ledger is a chain of many blocks of content. Each block has an associated unique number, which basically encode the whole information and consist in a hexadecimal hash. In addition, each block usually contains a link to a previous block. Therefore, results a chain of blocks distributed in a private or public network, governed by a set of predefined rules.

Transparency and immutability are fundamentals for the Blockchain technology. Once a data is recorded, nobody can change or delete it. Blockchain is also remarkable because it is a self-sustainable database with no central authority. Due to its characteristics, blockchain is a reliable solution for data storage and for ensuring traceability of an asset. Blockchain was design for cryptocurrencies but it can be successfully used in any industry because of its benefits.

Aviation industry manage sensitive information, in a system with various parties involved. Applying this technology to a supply chain would optimize this flow by reducing downtimes and deliver products just on time. Solutions based on blockchain technology are currently being explored to improve the sustainability of supply chains (Yash Madhwal & Peter B. Panfilov, 2017).

The international supply chains of the aviation industry are extremely complex. It generally involves many players in different stages of delivery and often rapid changes appears. For this reason, it is important to be able to clearly track the route or origin of the supply of a component. At present, the entities involve in the flow manage their own data separately, which can lead to confusion and miscommunication.

The IT systems of companies involved in a supply chain are not able to communicate with each other constantly. Therefore, ensuring the transparency and traceability of components involves the use of a secure common network such as Blockchain. This ensures immediate transparency of data in supply chains for all partners involved.

In the aviation industry there are various expensive aircraft's electronic components that need special storage and transportation conditions in terms of temperature, humidity and vibration. Having the ability

to not only monitor those parameters in real time of every electronic component but also share that information with all members in the supply chain is extremely useful.

In order to highlight the Blockchain concept and present how it can be applied in a real-life scenario, we developed an application using Python programming language. Its purpose was to create a chain of events associated to a supply chain activity. In a business to business situation, we assumed that an aircraft component supplier has to deliver an electronic component to an aircraft final assembly line, located cross-country. The asset was loaded onto a truck equipped with IoT sensors for temperature, humidity and vibration in order to be delivered. Every time the value of the three parameters has changed a new block was generated. Each block consists of a unique hash number("current_hash"), hash of the previous block ("previous_hash"), temperature, humidity, vibration, compliance status and a number called "nonce" which is used to verify the correctness of the Blockchain.

In the following figures, three stage of the developed Blockchain was presented:

- Figure 2: The initial block, also called genesis with no data stored;
- Figure 3: The second block that contain the first recorded data. Values of the recorded parameters are in the correct range, as a result the compliance status is "Compliant";
- Figure 4: The third block recorded a temperature above the normal value, therefore the compliance status is "Non-Compliant";

```
1 {
2   "chain": [
3     {
4       "SupplyChainParameters": [],
5       "current_hash": "8a080cea809d1b9d33b541f3498b1b6366ffc66df75423108947085057cf2f99",
6       "index": 1,
7       "nonce": 1,
8       "previous_hash": "0",
9       "timestamp": "2020-07-22 13:16:15.761889"
10    },
11  ],
12 }
```

Figure 2. The genesis block

```
11 {
12   "SupplyChainParameters": [
13     {
14       "ComplianceStatus": "Compliant",
15       "Humidity(%)": 55,
16       "Temperature(°C)": 39,
17       "Vibration(Hz)": 50
18     }
19   ],
20   "current_hash": "00042a67283d67d27b4d1f4245e59b93e304327a36e9c72a02645047c63dc55f",
21   "index": 2,
22   "nonce": 1969,
23   "previous_hash": "8a080cea809d1b9d33b541f3498b1b6366ffc66df75423108947085057cf2f99",
24   "timestamp": "2020-07-22 13:18:08.507097"
25 }
```

Figure 3. The second block – compliant data

```

26     {
27         "SupplyChainParameters": [
28             {
29                 "ComplianceStatus": "Non-Compliant",
30                 "Humidity(%)": 55,
31                 "Temperature(°C)": 79,
32                 "Vibration(Hz)": 50
33             }
34         ],
35         "current_hash": "000877944b1f87e0a2d0e58abebf46f2dc9fdac41649f7ba09bc701104b4ed62",
36         "index": 3,
37         "nonce": 16201,
38         "previous_hash": "00042a67283d67d27b4d1f4245e59b93e304327a36e9c72a02645047c63dc55f",
39         "timestamp": "2020-07-22 13:24:00.770575"
40     }
41 ],
42 "length": 3
43 }

```

Figure 4. The second block – non-compliant data

As it can be observed, the purpose of a Blockchain is to ensure traceability and transparency of an asset within a business network. Using this solution, quality will increase considerably, and some processes can be automated to reduce time and cost. In the presented scenario, the driver could be automatically notified to cancel the order and return to the original base to replace the damaged component.

Having the capability to ensure this kind of traceability of an aircraft components, not only throughout the supply chain but also throughout the fabrication, storage, repairing and operational period, will reduce counterfeiting and will increase the lifetime of the monitored components. All together, means saving time and money and safety improvements for aviation industry.

As a future work, the above theory will be implemented in a real case scenario in which we intend to equip a truck with a series of sensors for measuring temperature, humidity and vibration. The truck will transport aviation components from a Maintenance Repair and Overhaul supplier to an Aviation Maintenance Organization. The Data will be sent in a cloud infrastructure in real time in order to build a Blockchain structure. If some of the three parameters will exceed the established limits, the driver will be automatically notified on his mobile to cancel the transportation. The encountered challenges, technical details and results will be presented in a future article.

Conclusions

The fourth industrial revolution will certainly change business models. The most productive decisions are those based on the interpretation of data. Nowadays, the collection, storage and interpretation of data must be a priority for any competitive company. A relevant interpretation of these data can be made only by a total digitization within the organization and by using the latest technologies.

Well rooted concepts about quality improvement remain valid but their application need technology to be more efficient.

One of the most complex industry in the world is the aviation industry, where the need of innovation is more severe due to its complexity and safety requirements. Therefore, moving to the next level involves the use of artificial intelligence.

On top of that, creating an open platform, like Blockchain, to enable the secure and anonymous exchange of data for the aerospace industry, is the best management strategy today.

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